

The effects of microalgal feed supplementation on growth and digestive function of *Acipenser baerii* and *Sparus aurata*

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the potential use of microalgae, produced through a sustainable process, as protein and lipid source in practical diets for two commercially valuable fish species: Siberian sturgeon (*Acipenser baerii*) and gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*). To achieve this goal, the study evaluated different biomasses of *Microchloropsis gaditana*, cultivated on either conventional synthetic medium (MSM) or diluted pig manure (MPM), incorporated crude or hydrolysed into aquafeeds. Specifically, the impact on growth performance, digestive enzyme activity, and intestinal morphology was evaluated in both species. Regarding growth performance, no significant improvement was observed in sturgeon fed *M. gaditana*-supplemented diets. However, gilthead seabream significantly increased body weight except for the group fed diets elaborated with hydrolysed microalgae. Digestive enzyme activities were also modified by the use of algal biomass, with negative effects in Siberian sturgeon, whereas gilthead seabream proteolytic activities were enhanced, which evidenced a species-specific digestive response. Finally, morphological analyses of intestinal mucosa revealed that dietary inclusion of *M. gaditana* induced significant changes in both species. In Siberian sturgeon, the inclusion of microalgae reduced the total absorption surface, regardless of the growth medium used for producing the microalgae. Conversely, in gilthead seabream, dietary inclusion positively influenced intestinal morphology, increasing the intestinal fold diameter, enterocyte height, and microvilli length, indicating enhanced nutrient uptake capacity. In conclusion, these results evidenced the potential application of microalgae obtained from biorefinery as a protein and lipid source in practical diets for both fish species. However, the contrasting effects observed in both species bring to light the need for future works to assess the species-specific responses to dietary changes.

1. Introduction

During the last years, microalgae arise considerable interest in aquaculture due to their potential as a valuable source of dietary protein and bioactive compounds (Galafat et al., 2020; Galafat et al., 2022; Sáez et al., 2022). However, there are some technical gaps that must be addressed before functional algal-based ingredients can be effectively incorporated into commercial aquafeeds. In this regard, one of the main

bottlenecks is their high cost compared to regular feed ingredients. Indeed, the cost of microalgal biomasses proposed as functional ingredients for aquaculture purposes (*Microchloropsis gaditana* and *Tisochrysis lutea* above 100 USD kg⁻¹, or *Arthrospira platensis* around 15 USD kg⁻¹), is higher than that of fishmeal (1.6–2.2 USD kg⁻¹) (Galafat et al., 2021). Particularly, the specific nutrients requested for microalgae cultivation are expensive, and their cost ranges from 17.65 to 34.14 % of OPEX, so new strategies for improving production sustainability are

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requested (Lafarga, 2020; Vázquez-Romero et al., 2022).

In this context, several microalgal species can be grown on waste streams from agri-food industries, agriculture, and livestock (Acién Fernández et al., 2018). This offers the potential not only to reduce the production cost but also to recycle excess of nitrogen and phosphorus into protein, producing biomass that can be used as feed ingredient in aquaculture (Bongiorno et al., 2022). Algal biomass derived from agro-industrial wastewater are traditionally utilized for bioenergy production (Lage et al., 2018) or high-value agricultural products (Morillas-España et al., 2022). However, they constitute an interesting source of protein for aquafeeds but scarce information about this aspect is available (Dallaire et al., 2007; Van Den Hendel et al., 2016; Tomás-Almenar et al., 2018; Bongiorno et al., 2020; Bongiorno et al., 2022).

Additionally, the digestibility of algal nutrients can influence the growth of fish (Vizcaino et al., 2019). Overall, the structural polysaccharides present in the cell wall act as a physical barrier limiting the bioavailability of intracellular nutrients, which reduces the digestibility of algae (Bernaerts et al., 2018). The proportion of cellulose, hemicellulose, pectin, and glycoproteins changes among microalgae species (González-Fernández et al., 2011), and significantly affects nutrient accessibility to digestive enzymes (Scholz et al., 2014). Therefore, any strategy aimed at improving the bioavailability of the inner compounds might be of great interest for using algae in aquafeeds. In this regard, enzymatic hydrolysis of microalgae is a promising strategy not only because of its economic viability but also because it increases the nutritional and functional value of protein, yielding low molecular weight peptides, free amino acids, and bioactive peptides (Chalamaiah et al., 2012).

The use of microalgae-based ingredients in aquafeeds has gained increasing attention as a sustainable alternative to traditional protein sources, demonstrating promising benefits in both sturgeon and sparids. In Siberian sturgeon (*Acipenser baerii*), dietary use of biorefinery-derived microalgae has been successfully evaluated without compromising the growth performance, somatic indices, fillet nutritional composition, or intestinal functionality (Bongiorno et al., 2020). Furthermore, supplementation of feed with hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on diluted pig manure led to increase final weight of specimens, reinforcing its functional role in promoting growth and sustainability in aquaculture (Bongiorno et al., 2022). Similarly, 7.5 % dietary inclusion of *A. platensis* significantly improved survival rate, hematological parameters, and metabolic health indicators in Persian sturgeon (*Acipenser persicus*) larvae (Akhoundian et al., 2025). In gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*), microalgae-based ingredients have demonstrated functional benefits, contributing to nutritional quality, metabolic health, and microbiota interactions. The inclusion of a blend of *M. gaditana* and *A. platensis* improved protein and PUFA-n3 content, enhanced fillet texture and pigmentation, and delayed muscle lipid oxidation, particularly when enzymatically hydrolysed microalgae were used (Sáez et al., 2022). Additionally, replacing fish oil with microalgae-derived oil assured growth performance and fillet quality in this species (Santigosa et al., 2021). Beyond the nutritional aspects, microalgae supplementation influenced mucosal microbiota interactions in the skin and gills, enhancing microbial network resilience and identifying key taxa with potential protective roles against pathogens (Cerezo et al., 2024).

As stated above, Bongiorno et al. (2022) and Sáez et al. (2022) reported that 10 % and 5 % of dietary inclusion of *M. gaditana* in Siberian sturgeon and gilthead seabream, respectively, can be used as a functional ingredient without negatively impacting growth performance, proximate composition, and oxidative status in juvenile fish. In this piece of research, we aimed to compare the feasibility of utilizing both crude or hydrolysed *M. gaditana* biomass at the mentioned above dietary levels (10 % in Siberian sturgeon and 5 % in gilthead seabream), cultivated on standard nutrients or zootechnical wastewater effluents, as a functional ingredient for feeding these fish species. The work seeks to assess the effect of feeding fish with microalgae-supplemented diets on fish weight and intestinal functionality by analysing the digestive

enzymes and the structure and ultrastructure of the intestinal mucosa.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Microalgal biomass

The *Microchloropsis gaditana* biomass used was provided by the SABANA facilities at the University of Almería (Almería, Spain). The microalga was produced using a synthetic medium (SM) consisting of a solution of dissolved fertilizers in water, or diluted pig manure (PM), a solution of clean water plus manure (10 %). This dilution has been selected based on previous studies in other fish species (Tomás-Almenar et al., 2018), as it provides the same nutrients as those contained in a synthetic medium prepared with inorganic fertilizers. NaNO_3 , MgSO_4 , and KH_2PO_4 were used as fertilizers to provide a final concentration in both PM and SM of 200 mg L^{-1} nitrogen and 50 mg L^{-1} of phosphorus (Bongiorno et al., 2020). Microalgae were produced in outdoor thin-layer reactors operated in continuous mode under controlled conditions of pH and dissolved oxygen, solar radiation, and temperature varying as a function of the solar daylight cycle (Veuthey et al., 2022). Microalga biomass was harvested by centrifugation using a RINA centrifuge (Riera Nadeu SA, Spain). The harvested biomass was immediately frozen, freeze-dried, and milled to obtain a fine powder ($< 100 \mu\text{m}$) that was stored in the dark at -20°C until use.

2.2. Enzymatic hydrolysis of microalgae biomass

The different microalgal biomasses (MSM, crude protein: 35.8 %; crude lipid: 14.6 %; MPM, crude protein: 48.4 %; crude lipid: 18.6 %) were subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis using a mixture of commercial enzymes composed by carbohydrases (xylanase: $20,000 \text{ U g}^{-1}$ and glucanase; $30,000 \text{ U g}^{-1}$), cellulase ($10,000 \text{ U g}^{-1}$), and protease ($10,000 \text{ U g}^{-1}$) at an enzyme-to-algae ([E]/[S]) ratio of 0.05. Briefly, wet sludge of *M. gaditana* containing 200 g L^{-1} (dry weight, DW) was transferred into a 10 L reactor and incubated at 55°C under continuous agitation for 12 h in the presence of commercial enzymes. At the end of the biotechnological treatment algal biomasses were subjected to a pasteurization process at 72°C for 20 min, followed by freeze-drying before incorporation into the feed ingredient mix. The progression of the hydrolysis process was monitored by quantifying the amount of free amino acids and total reducing sugars released from the microalgae at different sampling times (0, 1, 2, 3, 6, and 12 h), following methods described by Church et al. (1983) and Miller (1959), respectively. In addition, SDS-PAGE electrophoresis gels were performed through the hydrolysis of microalgae at 0, 6, and 12 h (Laemmli, 1970). The chemical composition as well as the amino acids and fatty acids profiles of the crude and hydrolysed microalgal biomasses are detailed in Bongiorno et al. (2022).

2.3. Feed formulation and production

Two sets of five iso-nitrogenous and isolipidic experimental diets were formulated and manufactured by CEIMAR-University of Almería (Service of Experimental Diets) (Table 1). For the first feeding trial involving Siberian sturgeon, four experimental diets were formulated to include 10 % *M. gaditana* biomass, while a microalgae-free diet (CT) was also prepared as control. The level of dietary microalgal

Table 1
Nomenclature of the different experimental diets elaborated.

Diet	
CT	Microalgae-free diet, control
C-MSM	Untreated <i>M. gaditana</i> grown on Synthetic Medium (SM).
H-MSM	Hydrolysed <i>M. gaditana</i> grown on Synthetic Medium (SM).
C-MPM	Untreated <i>M. gaditana</i> grown on diluted Pig Manure (PM).
H-MPM	Hydrolysed <i>M. gaditana</i> grown on diluted Pig Manure (PM).

supplementation and the duration of the feeding assay (40 days) were set up according to the experimental design used by Bongiorno et al. (2022), who reported the effect of the same *M. gaditana* biomasses on the oxidative status in Siberian sturgeon juveniles. This study provided the scientific basis for maintaining the same experimental design, dietary inclusion level, and feeding period in the present study. For the second feeding trial involving gilthead seabream juvenile, four experimental diets were formulated to include 5 % *M. gaditana* biomass, alongside a microalgae-free control diet (CT). The inclusion level and feeding period (84 days) were selected based on the previous research done by Sáez et al. (2022), who evaluated the use of *M. gaditana* as a functional ingredient in this fish species. Their findings evidenced that a low dietary inclusion level (around 5 %) is a suitable nutritional strategy in *S. aurata* juveniles, justifying the dietary formulation used in the present study. The formulation and chemical composition of the experimental diets is presented in Table 2. The diet formulation was established considering the nutritional composition of the different algal biomasses (Supplementary Table 1) and the nutritional requirements of each species.

The experimental diets were manufactured using standard aquafeed processing procedures. Briefly, all ingredients were mixed in a 20 L mixer and ground with a hammer mill (UPZ 100, Hosokawa-Alpine, Augsburg, Germany) until 0.25 mm particles were obtained. At this point, it is important to note that the algal biomasses were subjected to a pasteurization process at 72 °C for 20 min, followed by freeze-drying before incorporation into the feed ingredient mix. Subsequently, the diets were extruded using a twin-screw extruder (Evoluum 25, Cletral, Firminy, France) equipped with dies suitable for the production of 1.0 to 2.0 mm in diameter and 2.0 to 3.0 mm in length sinking pellets. The extruder barrel consisted of four sections with temperature profiles of

100 °C, 95 °C, 95 °C, 95 °C, and 90 °C, respectively, along the sections. After extrusion, the pellets were dried at 30 °C in a 12 m³ drying chamber with forced air circulation (Airfrio, Almeria) and then cooled to room temperature. Vacuum oil coating was done on the following day in a Pegasus PG-10VC LAB vacuum coater (Dinnissen, The Netherlands). Then, feeds were kept in sealed plastic bags at -20 °C until use.

2.4. Feeding trial and sampling

Two feeding trials were performed in two fish species of commercial interest: i) Siberian sturgeon (*A. baerii*) and ii) gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*). Both feeding trials were carried out at the experimental facilities of the Istituto Sperimentale Italiano Lazzaro Spallanzani (Rivolta d'Adda, Italy).

2.4.1. Siberian sturgeon feeding trial

Following a 15-day acclimation period, 432 Siberian sturgeon fingerlings (average body weight 12.3 ± 0.1 g) were randomly distributed (32 fish per tank) into 15 fiberglass tanks of 120-L capacity in a recirculating aquaculture system. The experiment was carried out in triplicate (5 feeds × 3 tanks each feed) for 40 days. Fish were fed the different diets twice per day (9:00 am and 5:00 pm), 7 days per week at a rate of 3 % of their body weight. The trial was carried out in a flow-through filtered (1 µm) seawater system sterilized by UV, maintaining constant temperature (18.9 ± 0.6 °C), dissolved oxygen (9.4 ± 0.98 mg L⁻¹), pH (8.0 ± 0.1), NH₄-N (< 0.06 mg L⁻¹), NO₂-N (< 0.2 mg L⁻¹), with a 12 L:12D photoperiod.

At day 40, fish were individually weighed after a 12-h fasting period, under moderate anesthesia (MS222, 50 mg L⁻¹). At the end of the trial, six fish per tank (18 fish per dietary treatment) were randomly selected

Table 2
Ingredients and proximate composition (% dry weight) of the experimental diets used in the feeding trials.

	Siberian sturgeon					Gilthead seabream				
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM
<i>Ingredients (g per 100 g⁻¹ dry matter, DM)</i>										
Fish meal ¹	27.4	22.5	22.5	22.5	22.5	15	15	15	15	15
Soybean protein concentrate ²	25	25	25	25	25	27.3	24.4	24.4	24.4	24.4
Wheat meal ³	15	15	15	15	15	16	15.5	15.5	15.5	15.5
Microalgae ⁴	–	10	10	10	10	–	5	5	5	5
Attractant premix ⁵	10	10	10	10	10	–	–	–	–	–
CPSP 90 ⁶	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Fish oil	5	4.18	4.18	4.18	4.18	8	8	8	8	8
Wheat meal ⁷	4.05	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.31	16.6	15.4	15.4	15.4	15.4
Soybean oil	2.7	2.16	2.16	2.16	2.16	–	–	–	–	–
Rapeseed oil	–	–	–	–	–	4	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6
Linseed oil	–	–	–	–	–	1	1	1	1	1
Soy lecithin ⁸	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Vitamin and mineral premix ⁹	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2
Amino acid premix ¹⁰	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
Stay C Roche 0.2 %	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Choline chloride ⁸	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Calcium phosphate	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Binder	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	2	2	2	2	2
<i>Proximate composition (g kg⁻¹ dry matter, DM)</i>										
Crude protein	51.45	50.31	52.35	51.25	52.41	44.69	44.19	44.24	43.24	44.89
Crude lipid	13.96	13.25	13.96	13.81	14.60	19.23	19.23	19.57	18.93	19.46
Ash	7.61	9.11	8.16	9.60	8.46	7.88	9.44	9.12	9.86	9.28

Dietary codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); ¹ (protein: 69.4 %; lipids: 12.3 %) Norsildemel (Bergen, Noruega); ² (protein: 51.5 %; lipids: 8.0 %); ³ (protein: 76.0 %; lipids: 1.9 %); ⁴ (MSM, protein: 35.8 %; lipids: 14.6 %; MPM, protein: 48.4 %; lipids: 18.6 %); ⁵ (50 % squid meal, 50 % krill meal); ⁶ (protein: 84.1 %; lipids: 8.8 %), Sopropêche (France); ⁷ (protein: 12.0 %; lipids: 2.0 %); ⁸ (SigmaAldrich, Madrid, Spain); ⁹ Lifebioencapsulation SL (Almería, Spain). Vitamins (mg kg⁻¹): vitamin A (retinyl acetate), 2000,000 UI; vitamin D3 (DL-cholecalciferol), 200,000 UI; vitamin E (Lutavit E50), 10,000 mg; vitamin K3 (menadione sodium bisulfite), 2500 mg; vitamin B1 (thiamine hydrochloride), 3000 mg; vitamin B2 (riboflavin), 3000 mg; calcium pantothenate, 10,000 mg; nicotinic acid, 20,000 mg; vitamin B6 (pyridoxine hydrochloride), 2000 mg; vitamin B9 (folic acid), 1500 mg; vitamin B12 (cyanocobalamin), 10 mg vitamin H (biotin), 300 mg; inositol, 50,000 mg; betaine (Betafin S1), 50,000 mg. Minerals (mg kg⁻¹): Co (cobalt carbonate), 65 mg; Cu (cupric sulfate), 900 mg; Fe (iron sulfate), 600 mg; I (potassium iodide), 50 mg; Mn (manganese oxide), 960 mg; Se (sodium selenite), 1 mg; Zn (zinc sulfate) 750 mg; Ca (calcium carbonate), 18.6 %; (186,000 mg); KCl, 2.41 %; (24,100 mg); NaCl, 4.0 % (40,000 mg); ¹⁰ Lifebioencapsulation SL (Almería, Spain). Methionine:lysine:threonine ratio of 6:3:1.

and sacrificed by anesthetic overdose. The complete intestines were collected and differentiated into proximal and distal intestines. To determine digestive enzyme activities, individual intestinal samples were homogenized with ice-cold distilled water (w/v1:2) and supernatants were obtained after centrifugation ($13,000 \times g$, 12 min, 4°C) and stored at -20°C for further enzymatic analysis. In addition, the intestines of three specimens from each tank (9 fish per treatment) were collected for examination by light (LM), scanning (SEM), and transmission (TEM) electron microscopy. In all cases, 1 cm length portions of the proximal and distal intestines placed at 2 cm from the stomach and 2 cm from the anus, respectively, were collected from each fish.

2.4.2. Gilthead seabream feeding trial

The feeding trial was performed using 900 *S. aurata* juveniles (average 36.1 ± 0.02 g each) randomly allocated among 15 square-shaped 600-L fiberglass tanks (60 fish per tank) in a recirculating marine water system. After 15 days of acclimatization, dietary treatments were randomly assigned to tanks and tested in triplicate. Water parameters were monitored daily and kept constant and optimal for this species (temperature: 23.1°C , dissolved oxygen: 8.3 mg L^{-1}). Diets were offered in two daily meals per day (8:00 am and 4:00 pm) with a feed ratio between 2 and 3 % of body weight during 12 weeks of experimentation.

At the end of the feeding trial, fish were group-weighed after a 12-h fasting period, under moderate anesthesia (MS222, 50 mg L^{-1}). Six fish per tank (18 fish per dietary treatment) were sacrificed and dissected for intestinal tract (proximal and distal intestines) sampling and subsequent enzymatic activity and microscopy analysis as described above for Siberian sturgeon.

2.5. Analysis of digestive enzyme activities

Total alkaline protease activity in digestive extracts was quantified spectrophotometrically using buffered 5 g L^{-1} casein (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 9.0) as substrate according to Alarcón et al. (1998). One unit of total protease activity was defined as the amount of enzyme that released $1\text{ }\mu\text{g}$ of tyrosine per min (tyrosine extinction coefficient of $0.008\text{ }\mu\text{g}^{-1}\text{ mL}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) measured spectrophotometrically at 280 nm. Trypsin and chymotrypsin activities were measured using 0.5 mM BAPNA (N- α -benzoyl-DL-arginine-4-nitroanilide) as substrate following the method described by Erlanger et al. (1961), and 0.2 mM SAPNA (N-succinyl-(Ala)2-Pro-Phe-p-nitroanilide) according to DelMar et al. (1979), respectively. Leucine aminopeptidase activity was assayed using buffered 2 mM L-leucine-p-nitroanilide in (100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.8) as substrate according to Pfeleiderer (1970), and alkaline phosphatase was quantified using p-nitrophenyl phosphate in 1 M diethanolamine in 1 mM MgCl_2 buffer, (pH 9.5) as substrate (Bergmeyer, 1974). For trypsin, chymotrypsin, and leucine aminopeptidase activities, the amount of enzyme that released $1\text{ }\mu\text{mol}$ of p-nitroanilide per minute was defined as one unit of activity considering an extinction coefficient of 8800 M cm^{-1} measured at 405 nm. For alkaline phosphatase, one activity unit was defined as the amount of enzyme that released $1\text{ }\mu\text{g}$ of nitrophenyl per min considering an extinction coefficient of $17,800\text{ M cm}^{-1}$ for p-nitrophenol, measured at 405 nm. All assays were performed in triplicate, and specific enzymatic activity was expressed as units (U) g tissue $^{-1}$. In addition, digestive proteases in proximal and distal intestinal regions were separated and visualized in substrate-SDS-PAGE electrophoresis gels (Laemmli, 1970) and zymograms revealing protease active fractions were carried out following the procedures described by Alarcón et al. (1998).

2.6. Intestine histology

Intestine samples were fixed for 24 h in phosphate-buffered formalin (4 % v/v, pH 7.2), dehydrated, and embedded in paraffin according to standard histological techniques. Proximal and distal intestines were cut

in $7\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ transversal sections following the axis of the gut lumen, and the slides were stained with hematoxylin–eosin (H&E). The stained preparations were examined under a light microscope (OLYMPUS IX51) equipped with a digital camera CC 12 (Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions GmbH, Muenster, Germany), and the images were analyzed using the specific software ImageJ version 1.45 (National Institutes of Health Image software, Bethesda, MD). The length and the diameter of mucosa folds, the enterocyte height, as well as the thickness of lamina propria and the serosa, muscular, and submucosa layers were determined in the intestinal samples (50 independent measurements in the proximal and distal intestine per animal for 9 fish per treatment) (Supplementary Fig. 1).

2.7. Ultrastructural study of the intestinal mucosa

The intestine samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were fixed (4 h at 4°C) with phosphate-buffered glutaraldehyde 25 g L^{-1} and formaldehyde 40 g L^{-1} (pH 7.5), and then they were washed (three times for 20 min) with phosphate buffer saline. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), samples were previously washed with 1 % S-carboxymethyl-L-cysteine (Sigma) for 20 s to remove epithelial mucus and then fixed for 24 h in phosphate-buffered formalin (4 % v/v, pH 7.2). Both TEM and SEM preparations were processed according to standard electron microscopy techniques, as described in Vizcaíno et al. (2014). TEM observations were performed with a transmission electron microscope Zeiss 10C at 100 KV (Carl Zeiss, Barcelona, Spain). Visualization fields were recorded at $\times 16,000$ magnification, while SEM samples were screened with scanning electron microscopy (HITACHI model S-3500, Hitachi High-Technologies Corporation, Japan). Finally, TEM and SEM digital images were analyzed using the specific software ImageJ version 1.45 (National Institutes of Health Image software, Bethesda, MD). Microvilli length (ML), microvilli diameter (MD), and enterocyte apical area (EAA) were determined from TEM and SEM micrographs, and an estimation of the total absorption surface per enterocyte (TAS) was calculated according to Vizcaíno et al. (2014).

2.8. Statistical analysis

Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Data were tested for normality by the Shapiro-Wilk test and homogeneity of variances by the Levene test. When normality was not verified, data were transformed before ANOVA. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was used to determine differences in growth performance and digestive parameters among dietary groups. A Student's *t*-test was used to determine differences across intestinal sections. Finally, a two-way ANOVA was employed to assess the significant effects of fertilizer type, enzymatic hydrolysis treatment, and their interaction. Statistical analysis was done using GraphPad Prism version 9.3.0 software package for Windows (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Enzymatic hydrolysis of microalgae biomass

Fig. 1A shows the protein hydrolysis progression of *M. gaditana* biomasses cultivated in synthetic medium (SM) and diluted pig manure (PM) during the enzymatic treatment. Throughout the 12-h enzymatic hydrolysis, a slight degradation of some protein fractions was observed, while *M. gaditana* biomass showed a characteristic protein pattern in both its untreated (0 h) and hydrolysed (6 or 12 h) format. The quantification of reducing sugars indicated a progressive release of glucose concentration through the enzymatic treatment, with values reaching 8.7 g of glucose equivalents per 100 g of biomass at the end of the biotechnological enzymatic treatment in the case of *M. gaditana* grown in synthetic medium, SM (Fig. 1B). Conversely, lower glucose final concentration was observed when microalgae were cultivated in diluted

Fig. 1. (A) Evolution of enzymatic hydrolysis of *M. gaditana* grown in synthetic (SM) and diluted pig manure (PM) medium. Images show SDS-PAGE hydrolysis patterns obtained at each sampling point of the enzymatic treatment with commercial enzymes (0, 6, and 12 h). Marker: wide range molecular weight marker (Sigma marker S8445-10VL, 6500–200,000 Da, Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain). (B) Evolution of free glucose equivalents concentration during the enzymatic hydrolysis of *M. gaditana* grown in synthetic (SM) and diluted pig manure (PM) medium. (C) Evolution of total free amino acid concentration during the enzymatic hydrolysis of *M. gaditana* grown in synthetic (SM) and diluted pig manure (PM) medium. Values represented in graphs show the mean \pm SD of triplicate determinations ($n = 3$).

pig manure (PM). Lastly, Fig. 1C shows the availability of total free amino acids in the microalgal biomass. *M. gaditana* cultivated in PM evidenced higher values of total free amino acids (9.2 g leucine 100 g protein⁻¹) compared to algal biomass produced in SM (2.9 g leucine 100 g protein⁻¹).

3.2. Siberian sturgeon feeding trial

3.2.1. Growth performance

After 40 days of feeding experimental diets, Siberian sturgeons fed *M. gaditana*-supplemented diets showed no significant differences compared to the control group (CT) (Fig. 2, Supplementary Table 2). However, fish fed with the H-MPM diet exhibited the highest final body weight.

3.2.2. Digestive enzyme activities

The enzymatic activities in the proximal and distal intestine sections of Siberian sturgeon are detailed in Table 3 and Supplementary Table 3. The dietary inclusion of microalgae reduced the activity of chymotrypsin and alkaline phosphatase compared to the group fed without microalgae. Furthermore, a noticeable decrease was observed in the activities of leucine aminopeptidase and alkaline phosphatase in fish fed *M. gaditana* cultivated on pig manure (PM) compared to those fed with microalgae grown on synthetic medium (SM). Regarding the intestinal segment considered, alkaline phosphatase activity was higher in the proximal intestine, while total alkaline protease and leucine aminopeptidase activities were significantly higher in the distal intestine. No significant differences were found for enzymatic activities between fish-fed diets containing untreated or hydrolysed microalgal biomasses. Zymography analysis revealed similar patterns of alkaline protease in all dietary groups (Fig. 3).

3.2.3. Histological and ultrastructural study of the intestinal mucosa

Histomorphological data obtained from the analysis of images by light microscopy are presented in Table 4 and Supplementary Table 4. In general, the inclusion of microalgae in feed altered the diameter and

Fig. 2. Final body weight of Siberian sturgeon fed the experimental diets over 40 days. Dietary codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM). Data represent mean ± SEM (n = 3). Different letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

Table 3

Digestive enzyme activity (U g tissue⁻¹) in the proximal and distal intestine of Siberian sturgeon fed the experimental diets.

	Proximal intestine					P value
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	
TAP	618.82 ± 8.06 ^a	457.19 ± 8.53 ^b	571.07 ± 10.10 ^{ab}	529.97 ± 7.49 ^{ab}	496.20 ± 5.65 ^{ab}	0.0184
TRY	1.78 ± 0.09	2.01 ± 0.01	1.54 ± 0.01	1.84 ± 0.01	2.09 ± 0.11	0.4479
CHY	8.31 ± 0.18	5.38 ± 0.05	6.14 ± 0.05	7.80 ± 0.33	7.75 ± 1.16	0.7786
LA	0.16 ± 0.00 ^b	0.14 ± 0.00 ^{bc}	0.11 ± 0.00 ^{bc}	0.24 ± 0.01 ^a	0.08 ± 0.01 ^c	0.0003
AP	16.53 ± 0.13 ^a	15.47 ± 0.10 ^a	9.09 ± 0.09 ^c	12.75 ± 0.09 ^b	8.85 ± 0.14 ^c	< 0.0001
	Distal intestine					
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	P value
TAP	673.77 ± 12.09 ^a	624.76 ± 1.64 ^{ab}	630.43 ± 10.07 ^{ab}	504.59 ± 13.15 ^b	642.87 ± 3.91 ^{ab}	0.0348
TRY	2.17 ± 0.06 ^{ab}	1.76 ± 0.06 ^{ab}	2.44 ± 0.04 ^a	2.31 ± 0.09 ^a	1.25 ± 0.02 ^b	0.0119
CHY	9.85 ± 0.01 ^a	5.13 ± 0.07 ^b	9.13 ± 0.08 ^a	3.99 ± 0.21 ^b	3.43 ± 0.23 ^b	< 0.0001
LA	0.27 ± 0.01 ^a	0.18 ± 0.00 ^{ab}	0.24 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	0.33 ± 0.01 ^a	0.10 ± 0.01 ^b	0.0110
AP	13.35 ± 0.48 ^a	7.94 ± 0.20 ^b	8.78 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	10.03 ± 0.10 ^{ab}	7.59 ± 0.35 ^b	0.0162

Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); TAP: total alkaline protease; TRY: trypsin; CHY: chymotrypsin; LA: leucine aminopeptidase; AP: alkaline phosphatase. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was used to determine differences among dietary groups. Data represent mean ± SEM. Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

thickness of lamina propria in fish intestines. Fish-fed microalgae-supplemented diet showed a decrease in the diameter of intestinal folds but an increase in the thickness of lamina propria compared to those that did not receive microalgae supplementation. Furthermore, the type of culture medium used for producing the microalgal biomass influenced all evaluated parameters. Fish-fed diets containing microalgae produced on manure showed a significant increase in fold length and enterocyte height. However, in these fish, the diameter of intestinal folds and thickness of lamina propria and muscular layer were significantly lower. Finally, hydrolysis treatment applied to algal biomass did not appear to affect fold length in fish fed this diet. However, an increase in enterocyte height and lamina propria thickness was observed, as well as a decrease in fold diameter and muscular layer thickness.

Visual examination of SEM and TEM images confirmed that the experimental diets did not cause structural damage to the microvilli (Fig. 4, Supplementary Fig. 2). The epithelium of the intestinal mucosa exhibited numerous mucous cells and was composed of both columnar ciliated and non-ciliated cells. Ciliated cells displayed distinctive tufts of microvilli and cilia, while non-ciliated cells exhibited microvilli forming the brush border (Supplementary Fig. 3).

Ultrastructural analysis of proximal and distal intestinal sections is presented in Table 5 and Supplementary Table 5. In general, the dietary incorporation of microalgae resulted in a reduction in the total absorption surface compared to the group fed without microalgae, while no effects were observed on microvilli length, microvilli diameter, and enterocyte apical area. Moreover, a significant increase in microvilli length and absorption surface, along with a statistical decrease in microvilli diameter, was observed in fish fed *M. gaditana* cultivated on synthetic medium (SM) compared to those fed microalgae grown on diluted pig manure (PM). Regarding the intestinal segment, in the distal intestine, microvilli length was statistically higher, whereas enterocyte apical area and absorption surface were statistically higher in the

Fig. 3. Zymograms of alkaline proteases in the proximal (A) and distal (B) intestinal segments of Siberian sturgeon fed the experimental diets over 40 days. Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM).

Table 4
Histological parameters assessed in the proximal intestine of Siberian sturgeon fed the experimental diets.

	Proximal intestine					P value
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	
FL (µm)	925.45 ± 8.98 ^b	808.13 ± 9.91 ^b	885.92 ± 20.69 ^b	617.62 ± 7.35 ^c	1027.83 ± 13.81 ^a	< 0.0001
FD (µm)	80.62 ± 1.13 ^a	75.66 ± 0.94 ^{ab}	80.01 ± 1.36 ^{ab}	73.73 ± 1.36 ^b	43.81 ± 0.81 ^c	< 0.0001
EH (µm)	35.64 ± 0.56 ^b	33.89 ± 0.55 ^b	28.93 ± 0.54 ^c	28.99 ± 0.53 ^c	43.76 ± 0.59 ^a	< 0.0001
ML (µm)	84.65 ± 0.73 ^c	104.95 ± 1.31 ^a	71.37 ± 1.16 ^d	94.20 ± 1.43 ^b	38.25 ± 0.56 ^e	< 0.0001
LP (µm)	8.49 ± 0.42 ^b	8.42 ± 0.25 ^b	8.34 ± 0.30 ^b	11.52 ± 0.49 ^b	14.97 ± 0.42 ^a	< 0.0001

Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); FL: fold length; FD: fold diameter; EH: enterocyte height; ML: muscular layer; LP: lamina propria. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test was used to determine differences among dietary groups. Data represent mean ± SEM. Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

proximal intestine. Additionally, no morphological differences were found between diets containing untreated or hydrolysed microalgae.

3.3. Gilthead seabream feeding trial

3.3.1. Growth performance

At the end of the 12-week feeding trial, gilthead seabream fed with *M. gaditana*-supplemented diets exhibited higher final body weight compared to those fed the CT diet, except for fish fed the H-MSM diet (Fig. 5, Supplementary Table 2).

3.3.2. Digestive enzyme activities

The enzymatic activities in the proximal and distal intestinal sections of gilthead seabream are detailed in Table 6 and Supplementary Table 6. Overall, the use of microalgae appeared to increase marginally the activity of the digestive enzymes measured. There were neither significant differences in enzymatic activities between fish-fed diets containing untreated or hydrolysed microalgae nor between fish-fed diets containing microalgae grown on synthetic medium (SM) or pig manure (PM). Regarding the intestinal segment, alkaline phosphatase activity was higher in the proximal intestine, while total alkaline protease, trypsin, chymotrypsin, and leucine aminopeptidase activities were higher in the distal intestine. Zymography analysis revealed a similar pattern of intestinal proteases in fish fed the microalgae-supplemented diets compared to fish of the control group (Fig. 6).

3.3.3. Histological and ultrastructural study of the intestinal mucosa

The histomorphological analysis evidenced that the inclusion of microalgae provoked a significant effect in both the proximal and distal intestinal sections (Table 7 and Supplementary Table 7). Neither inflammatory processes nor accumulation of lipid vacuoles inside the enterocytes was observed, which indicates the absence of intestinal enteritis or steatosis. Overall, the inclusion of microalgae in gilthead seabream diets increased intestinal fold diameter and enterocyte height, while reduced the thickness of the muscular and submucosa layers as well as the lamina propria. Moreover, a significant reduction in fold diameter and enterocyte height, as well as the thickness of the serosa and muscular layers, was observed in fish fed *M. gaditana* cultivated on synthetic medium (SM) compared to those fed microalgae grown on pig manure (PM). The use of hydrolysed biomass reduced significantly all the histological parameters measured. Finally, statistically higher values in all parameters assessed were obtained in the distal intestine of gilthead seabream, except for the submuscular layer, which was higher in the proximal intestine.

The observation of images obtained through SEM and TEM revealed that none of the experimental diets tested caused damage to the fish intestinal mucosa (Fig. 7, Supplementary Fig. 4).

The ultrastructural analysis of the intestinal mucosa of gilthead seabream specimens fed the experimental diets is presented in Table 8 and Supplementary Table 8. Results evidenced that dietary inclusion of microalgae increased microvilli length and total absorption surface compared to the control group, accompanied by a reduction in microvilli diameter. Furthermore, a significant increase in microvillar parameters,

Fig. 4. Comparative TEM micrographs from the (A) proximal and (B) distal intestine of Siberian sturgeon fed the experimental diets over 40 days. Images detail the ultrastructure of the enterocyte brush border membrane. Scale bar: 1 μm . Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM).

except for the enterocyte apical area, was observed in fish fed *M. gaditana* cultivated on synthetic medium (SM) compared to those fed microalgae grown on pig manure (PM). The inclusion of hydrolysed *M. gaditana* significantly increased microvilli length and reduced enterocyte apical area and total absorption surface compared to the use of untreated algal biomass. Regarding intestinal segments, the magnitude of microvillar parameters in the proximal intestine was higher than in the distal section.

4. Discussion

The growth performance results obtained in this study highlight the species-specific effects of *M. gaditana* supplementation, which can be attributed to various factors, including differences in physiological and nutritional requirements, dietary inclusion levels, and feeding trial durations. While Siberian sturgeon did not exhibit significant differences in

final body weight between the control and *M. gaditana*-supplemented groups, gilthead seabream generally improved growth performance, except for those fed the H-MSM diet. This suggests that *M. gaditana* biomass may enhance growth in gilthead seabream, possibly due to improved nutrient bioavailability resulting from enzymatic hydrolysis or the composition of the PM biomass itself. The enzymatic treatment and nutrient source (zootechnical wastewater effluents) may have contributed to increasing the digestibility and accessibility of essential nutrients, thereby facilitating more efficient nutrient utilization in seabream compared to sturgeon.

The differences in dietary inclusion levels (10 % in sturgeon vs. 5 % in seabream) were based on prior research. Sáez et al. (2022) reported that 5 % or lower *M. gaditana* inclusion is suitable for gilthead seabream juveniles, while Bongiorno et al. (2022) found that 10 % inclusion did not negatively impact growth in Siberian sturgeon. Additionally, the feeding trial durations (40 days for sturgeon and 84 days for seabream)

Table 5
Microvillar morphology in the proximal and distal intestine of Siberian sturgeon fed the experimental diets.

	Proximal intestine					P value
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	
ML (µm)	2.40 ± 0.02 ^d	3.04 ± 0.03 ^b	2.46 ± 0.03 ^d	2.82 ± 0.03 ^c	3.40 ± 0.03 ^a	< 0.0001
MD (nm)	96.88 ± 0.25 ^b	98.70 ± 0.24 ^b	103.40 ± 0.18 ^a	102.18 ± 0.15 ^{ab}	107.14 ± 0.21 ^a	< 0.0001
EAA (µm ²)	46.21 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	50.19 ± 0.24 ^a	44.25 ± 0.18 ^b	43.20 ± 0.21 ^b	37.34 ± 0.17 ^c	< 0.0001
TAS (µm ²)	3023.16 ± 12.01 ^b	3454.69 ± 1.69 ^a	2120.71 ± 8.83 ^c	2650.70 ± 13.22 ^b	2812.28 ± 12.64 ^b	< 0.0001
	Distal intestine					
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	P value
ML (µm)	3.44 ± 0.03 ^b	3.70 ± 0.04 ^a	2.82 ± 0.04 ^c	2.95 ± 0.03 ^d	3.18 ± 0.04 ^c	< 0.0001
MD (nm)	105.80 ± 0.18 ^a	107.72 ± 0.23 ^a	103.18 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	96.86 ± 0.16 ^c	100.00 ± 0.21 ^{bc}	< 0.0001
EAA (µm ²)	39.04 ± 0.25 ^a	27.33 ± 0.17 ^b	37.04 ± 0.18 ^a	38.54 ± 0.15 ^a	41.16 ± 0.14 ^a	< 0.0001
TAS (µm ²)	2571.78 ± 16.37 ^{ab}	1907.63 ± 11.93 ^c	2358.13 ± 11.68 ^b	2924.08 ± 10.94 ^a	1847.25 ± 6.32 ^b	< 0.0001

Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); ML: microvilli length; MD: microvilli diameter; EAA: enterocyte apical area; TAS: enterocyte absorption surface. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was used to determine differences among dietary groups. Data represent mean ± SEM. Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 5. Final body weight of gilthead seabream fed the experimental diets over 12 weeks. Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM). Data represent mean ± SEM (n = 3). Different letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

were determined based on these studies. In this sense, previous studies have demonstrated that microalgae supplementation in aquafeeds can have both beneficial and adverse effects, depending on the species, inclusion level, and feeding duration (Xu et al., 2014; Sørensen et al., 2016; Vizcaíno et al., 2018; Skalli et al., 2020; García-Márquez et al., 2023).

The differences in dietary formulation (10 % vs. 5 % *M. gaditana*), along with variations in fishmeal inclusion (22.5–27.4 % in sturgeon vs. 15 % in seabream), may have contributed to the variations in growth responses. Notably, despite the higher fishmeal content in sturgeon diets, no significant improvements in growth performance were observed. This suggests that a 10 % *M. gaditana* inclusion level may not be optimal for this sturgeon, potentially due to digestibility limitations or inefficient nutrient utilization. In contrast, gilthead seabream benefited from *M. gaditana* supplementation, indicating that lower inclusion rates may be more suitable for optimizing the growth and

Table 6
Digestive enzyme activity (U g tissue⁻¹) in the proximal and distal intestine of gilthead seabream fed the experimental diets.

	Proximal intestine					P value
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	
TAP	843.5 ± 10.60 ^c	1013.21 ± 11.01 ^b	879.51 ± 4.34 ^{bc}	952.27 ± 12.01 ^{bc}	1180.29 ± 16.20 ^a	< 0.0001
TRY	0.30 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	0.32 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	0.24 ± 0.01 ^b	0.26 ± 0.01 ^b	0.36 ± 0.01 ^a	0.0051
CHY	4.95 ± 0.08 ^c	6.87 ± 0.09 ^b	6.08 ± 0.08 ^{bc}	8.35 ± 0.10 ^a	6.70 ± 0.08 ^b	< 0.0001
LA	0.27 ± 0.01	0.30 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.01	0.0663
AP	4.75 ± 0.06 ^{ab}	4.89 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	4.40 ± 0.07 ^{ab}	4.10 ± 0.04 ^b	5.02 ± 0.07 ^a	0.0251
	Distal intestine					
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	P value
TAP	2228.59 ± 24.25 ^c	2731.42 ± 23.39 ^a	2425.56 ± 16.38 ^{bc}	2506.60 ± 16.34 ^{ab}	2519.46 ± 14.39 ^{ab}	0.0001
TRY	0.82 ± 0.01 ^b	1.06 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	1.12 ± 0.02 ^a	0.84 ± 0.02 ^b	0.88 ± 0.02 ^b	0.0015
CHY	19.45 ± 0.18 ^b	22.33 ± 0.15 ^{ab}	20.06 ± 0.17 ^b	23.36 ± 0.29 ^a	22.04 ± 0.22 ^{ab}	0.0023
LA	0.41 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.03	0.40 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.01	0.8590
AP	4.50 ± 0.05	4.36 ± 0.06	3.96 ± 0.05	4.42 ± 0.07	4.23 ± 0.04	0.2956

Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); TAP: total alkaline protease; TRY: trypsin; CHY: chymotrypsin; LA: leucine aminopeptidase; AP: alkaline phosphatase. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was used to determine differences among dietary groups. Data represent mean ± SEM. Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

intestinal health in this species.

Feed conversion ratio (FCR) results further support these findings. In Siberian sturgeon, no significant differences in FCR values were observed compared to the control, except for the H-MPM group, which achieved the best results (Bongiorno et al., 2022). In gilthead seabream, statistically lower FCR values were observed in fish-fed PM-derived biomasses (C-MPM and H-MPM) (Bongiorno et al., 2021). These results reinforce the idea that nutrient digestibility and utilization efficiency may vary significantly depending on the species and the type of microalgal biomass included in the diet. Thus, this discrepancy highlights the different responses of various species to dietary interventions

Fig. 6. Zymograms of alkaline proteases in the proximal (A) and distal (B) intestine of gilthead seabream fed the experimental diets over 12 weeks. Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM).

Table 7

Histological parameters assessed in the proximal and distal intestine of gilthead seabream fed on experimental diets.

	Proximal intestine					P value
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	
FD (µm)	99.80 ± 0.31	92.70 ± 1.74	99.38 ± 0.24	97.15 ± 0.22	97.14 ± 0.36	0.0676
EH (µm)	35.72 ± 0.09 ^d	36.51 ± 0.08 ^{cd}	43.52 ± 0.08 ^a	40.70 ± 0.09 ^b	38.46 ± 0.10 ^{bc}	< 0.0001
SL (µm)	45.60 ± 0.21 ^c	75.43 ± 0.41 ^a	54.87 ± 0.32 ^{bc}	54.63 ± 0.40 ^{bc}	60.60 ± 0.28 ^b	< 0.0001
ML (µm)	85.24 ± 0.42 ^a	86.57 ± 0.15 ^a	76.54 ± 0.48 ^{ab}	72.71 ± 0.42 ^b	82.54 ± 0.31 ^{ab}	0.0005
SBL (µm)	48.53 ± 0.23 ^a	35.73 ± 0.24 ^b	41.88 ± 0.16 ^a	40.12 ± 0.20 ^{ab}	37.44 ± 0.16 ^{ab}	< 0.0001
LP (µm)	15.88 ± 0.06 ^a	12.28 ± 0.04 ^{bc}	13.11 ± 0.06 ^b	11.62 ± 0.05 ^c	12.83 ± 0.05 ^{bc}	< 0.0001
	Distal intestine					
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	P value
FD (µm)	106.00 ± 0.35 ^c	119.75 ± 0.42 ^{ab}	129.92 ± 0.40 ^a	113.98 ± 0.29 ^{bc}	115.18 ± 0.43 ^{bc}	< 0.0001
EH (µm)	46.24 ± 0.17 ^{bc}	42.76 ± 0.09 ^c	55.27 ± 0.11 ^a	43.66 ± 0.09 ^{bc}	46.84 ± 0.15 ^b	< 0.0001
SL (µm)	103.93 ± 0.58 ^b	104.84 ± 0.26 ^{ab}	105.10 ± 0.43 ^{ab}	47.58 ± 0.16 ^c	114.29 ± 0.25 ^a	< 0.0001
ML (µm)	119.38 ± 0.44 ^a	107.97 ± 0.28 ^b	105.16 ± 0.30 ^{bc}	53.58 ± 0.23 ^d	99.24 ± 0.16 ^c	< 0.0001
SBL (µm)	39.78 ± 0.19 ^a	40.93 ± 0.15 ^a	41.83 ± 0.22 ^a	33.41 ± 0.26 ^b	38.56 ± 0.11 ^a	0.0005
LP (µm)	18.90 ± 0.05 ^a	14.85 ± 0.08 ^c	17.80 ± 0.09 ^{ab}	16.59 ± 0.06 ^{bc}	14.56 ± 0.04 ^c	< 0.0001

Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); FD: fold diameter; EH: enterocyte height; SL: serosa layer; ML: muscular layer; SBL: submucosa layer; LP: lamina propria. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test was used to determine differences among dietary groups. Data represent mean ± SEM. Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

and the importance of taking into account species-specific dietary requirements. The variability in the growth of the two species emphasizes the need to adapt specific feeding strategies to optimize growth and nutritional outcomes in aquaculture.

The variations in digestive enzyme activity observed in the proximal and distal intestinal sections of Siberian sturgeon and gilthead seabream provide valuable insights into the effects of dietary supplementation with *M. gaditana* biomass for each species. The differentiation between proximal and distal intestinal segments is essential, as digestion occurs in distinct phases along the digestive tract (Moraes and de Almeida, 2020). The proximal intestine is primarily responsible for the initial hydrolysis of macronutrients, where enzymatic activity is typically higher to facilitate the breakdown of proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids. In contrast, the distal intestine plays a crucial role in the final stages of digestion and nutrient absorption, particularly in the uptake of peptides, amino acids, and other hydrolysis-derived nutrients. Therefore, assessing enzyme activity across these sections allows for a more comprehensive understanding of how dietary modifications influence digestive efficiency and nutrient utilization. The results of this study suggest that

M. gaditana supplementation modulates digestive enzyme activity in a species-dependent manner, likely reflecting differences in digestive physiology and nutrient assimilation strategies between sturgeon and seabream.

The digestive physiology of *A. baerii* and *S. aurata* differs due to their feeding habits and digestive tract morphology, which in turn influences their digestive responses to diets. *A. baerii* possesses a relatively short and straight digestive tract with limited specialization, reflecting its adaptation to a protein-rich, animal-based diet (Chebanov and Galich, 2018). Its enzymatic profile is dominated by high proteolytic activity, with relatively lower amylase and lipase activities, consistent with its reliance on easily digestible animal proteins and fats (Falahatkar, 2018). In contrast, *S. aurata* has a more complex and regionally specialized digestive system, including a developed stomach, pyloric caeca, and a longer intestinal tract adapted to a mixed diet of animal and plant material (García Hernández et al., 2001; Elbal et al., 2004). This species exhibits a more balanced enzymatic activity profile, with substantial amylase, lipase, and protease levels that allow efficient utilization of carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins (Gilannejad et al., 2021).

Fig. 7. Comparative TEM micrographs from the (A) proximal and (B) distal intestine of gilthead seabream fed the experimental diets. Images detail the ultrastructure of the enterocyte brush border membrane. Scale bar: 1 μm . Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM).

From a metabolic perspective, the protein and energy requirements of *A. baerii* are higher and more rigid, particularly in juveniles, making it more sensitive to suboptimal amino acid profiles and less digestible feed components (Falahaatkar, 2018). In contrast, *S. aurata* exhibits more dietary plasticity and can better adapt to alternative feed ingredients (Perera et al., 2019). These interspecific differences may help explain the variable digestive responses to the dietary inclusion of *M. gaditana* observed in our study, particularly in terms of digestive enzyme activities and intestinal morphology, and highlight the need for species-specific formulation strategies when incorporating novel functional ingredients into aquafeeds.

In Siberian sturgeon, the inclusion of microalgae appeared to reduce digestive enzyme activity, whereas in gilthead seabream, it seemed to enhance enzymatic activity. This contrasting response suggests species-specific adaptations in digestive physiology to dietary changes, potentially influenced by the different dietary inclusion levels tested in each feeding trial. The increased enzymatic activity observed in seabream may contribute to improved digestive functionality, potentially supporting enhanced growth, as reported in previous studies (Vizcaino et al., 2014; Qiao et al., 2019; García-Márquez et al., 2022). Conversely, the reduction in enzymatic activity observed in Siberian sturgeon was not associated with growth impairment, which may indicate the

Table 8
Microvillar morphology in the proximal and distal intestine of gilthead seabream fed the experimental diets.

	Proximal intestine					
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	P value
ML (μm)	1.76 \pm 0.01 ^c	2.23 \pm 0.01 ^a	2.25 \pm 0.01 ^a	2.21 \pm 0.01 ^a	1.98 \pm 0.02 ^b	< 0.0001
MD (nm)	106.89 \pm 0.19 ^b	114.16 \pm 0.24 ^a	106.88 \pm 0.14 ^b	112.56 \pm 0.20 ^a	112.36 \pm 0.19 ^a	0.0001
EAA (μm^2)	19.47 \pm 0.08 ^b	22.99 \pm 0.07 ^a	21.21 \pm 0.08 ^b	16.90 \pm 0.04 ^c	19.58 \pm 0.04 ^b	< 0.0001
TAS (μm^2)	699.27 \pm 2.10 ^d	1103.11 \pm 3.29 ^a	918.47 \pm 2.69 ^b	768.57 \pm 1.68 ^c	783.75 \pm 1.47 ^c	< 0.0001
	Distal intestine					
	CT	C-MSM	C-MPM	H-MSM	H-MPM	P value
ML (μm)	1.97 \pm 0.02 ^c	2.06 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.65 \pm 0.06 ^d	2.38 \pm 0.05 ^a	1.95 \pm 0.02 ^c	< 0.0001
MD (nm)	111.51 \pm 0.19 ^a	111.87 \pm 0.18 ^a	99.16 \pm 0.22 ^b	108.50 \pm 0.27 ^a	101.06 \pm 0.17 ^b	< 0.0001
EAA (μm^2)	13.53 \pm 0.06 ^b	16.04 \pm 0.03 ^a	12.05 \pm 0.03 ^c	13.10 \pm 0.04 ^b	12.87 \pm 0.03 ^b	< 0.0001
TAS (μm^2)	408.55 \pm 1.89 ^c	708.33 \pm 1.53 ^a	303.33 \pm 0.78 ^d	562.94 \pm 1.57 ^b	436.42 \pm 0.90 ^c	< 0.0001

Codes: CT (control diet); C-MSM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on SM); C-MPM (Untreated *M. gaditana* grown on PM); H-MSM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on SM); H-MPM (Hydrolysed *M. gaditana* grown on PM); ML: microvilli length; MD: microvilli diameter; EAA: enterocyte apical area; TAS: enterocyte absorption surface. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was used to determine differences among dietary groups. Data represent mean \pm SEM. Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

presence of compensatory mechanisms in response to dietary modifications (Santigosa et al., 2008; Vizcaíno et al., 2016). Bongiorno et al. (2022) similarly reported no adverse effects on zootechnical parameters when Siberian sturgeon was fed a diet containing 10 % *M. gaditana*.

Interestingly, the absence of significant differences in enzymatic activities between fish fed diets containing untreated or hydrolysed microalgae suggests that enzymatic hydrolysis may not substantially influence overall enzymatic activity in the digestive tract in both species. Furthermore, the distribution of enzymatic activities along the intestinal sections differed between the two species, with alkaline phosphatase activity being statistically higher in the proximal intestine, while total alkaline protease and leucine aminopeptidase activities were higher in the distal intestine. These findings highlight the importance of intestinal regionalization in assessing digestive physiology in aquatic species.

The inclusion of microalgal biomass in fish diets has been shown to have a significant impact on intestinal health and morphology (Jorge et al., 2019; Messina et al., 2019; Bongiorno et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2024). In this study, results from both Siberian sturgeon and gilthead seabream demonstrated an increase in the diameter of intestinal folds and enterocyte height, suggesting an improvement in intestinal health and nutrient absorption capacity (Messina et al., 2019). Similar results were reported by Sáez et al. (2022) when crude and hydrolysed *M. gaditana* biomass were included in gilthead seabream diets. The species-specific differences observed highlight the need for tailored feeding strategies in aquaculture to account for the unique physiological characteristics of different species.

Significant alterations in intestinal morphology due to microalgae inclusion were observed in both species. In Siberian sturgeon, the dietary incorporation of microalgae resulted in a significant reduction in total absorption surface compared to the control group. Conversely, in gilthead seabream, the inclusion of microalgae significantly increased microvilli length and total absorption surface compared to the control group. These contrasting responses highlight variations in intestinal morphology in response to dietary changes between both species and reinforce the importance of considering species-specific dietary requirements, digestive physiology, and stages of development in aquaculture practices.

Additional differences in intestinal morphology were observed based on microalgal growing conditions and treatments. In both species, fish fed *M. gaditana* cultivated in synthetic medium (SM) exhibited significantly higher microvilli length and absorption surface compared to those fed microalgae grown on pig manure (PM). Furthermore, while no morphological differences were observed between diets containing crude or hydrolysed microalgae in Siberian sturgeon, gilthead seabream fed hydrolysed *M. gaditana* significantly increased microvilli length but reduced enterocyte apical area and total absorption surface compared to

the inclusion of crude microalgae. These differences in intestinal morphology suggest that whole *M. gaditana* could have acted not only as a direct nutrient source but also as a prebiotic, influencing gut microbiota composition and indirectly supporting gut morphology. Whole microalgae contain complex polysaccharides, fiber, and bioactive compounds that may not be fully digestible by fish but may serve as substrates for microbial fermentation, potentially promoting beneficial bacterial populations (Jorge et al., 2019). This could explain the higher morphometric values observed in gilthead seabream intestinal histology despite no significant effects on digestive enzyme activity being evidenced. However, in Siberian sturgeon, it is possible that the short duration of algal supplementation was insufficient to induce measurable benefits, particularly if microalgal effects are mediated through gradual microbial community shifts. Unlike direct nutrient absorption, which can lead to more immediate physiological responses, the prebiotic-like effects of microalgae may require a longer adaptation period for microbial populations to shift and for associated morphological and functional improvements to manifest (Butt and Volkoff, 2019). To further explore this hypothesis, future studies should incorporate metagenomic analyses to determine whether microbial modifications played a role in the observed morphological changes over time.

In conclusion, our study highlights the potential of the different tested biomasses of *M. gaditana* as a functional ingredient in aquaculture, with promising results for improving the growth and intestinal health in gilthead seabream. However, the effects observed in Siberian sturgeon emphasize the need for species-specific evaluation, as *M. gaditana* supplementation did not enhance growth or digestive functionality in this species, which suggests the need for testing lower dietary inclusion levels in further studies. Collectively, these findings illustrate the complexity of integrating novel ingredients such as microalgae into aquafeeds and reinforce the importance of tailoring feed formulations to meet the unique physiological requirements of different species. Future research should focus on optimizing the dietary inclusion levels of *M. gaditana* for both species. Specifically, in Siberian sturgeon, testing lower supplementation levels (e.g., 5 %) may reveal potential growth-promoting effects that were not evident at higher inclusion rates. Similarly, in gilthead seabream, additional trials at lower inclusion rates (e.g., 2.5 %) could determine if the positive effects on growth and intestinal health are sustained, which would support the cost-effective and efficient use of microalgae in aquafeeds. Such studies could pave the way for refining microalgae-based feeds to maximize their benefits in sustainable aquaculture practices.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

None of the authors have a conflict of interest to disclose.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2025.742920>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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